

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Saqiboeva Durdona Bozorboevna

ORGANIZATIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF

DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

TAQDIRLANADI

zenodo

2023/YANVAR

